
Analyze the level of stress among the teaching faculty in private colleges at the time accreditation purpose with special reference to Chennai district

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ABSTRACT

This paper identifies the stress level of academic faculty and their influence towards the top authority at time accreditation period. The study approaches the various level of stress in top private colleges (25Nos) in Chennai district. Quantitative research techniques were adopted with specific tertiary institution in Chennai was used to draw sample from the total population. Total sample of 115 retrieved questionnaire by accidental sample techniques were used for data collection. Among 115 sample 82% responded gave their proper rating were taken into consideration for research purpose. Data analysis tools multiple regression, standard deviation and multivariate regression analysis were taken into consideration, among the tools and techniques the majority of respondent emphasis the health-related stress activities to be given for the faculty.

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Introduction:

Stress is one of the unavoidable components of normal life. It is a psychological state. The term stress has been derived from the Latin word 'stringer'; which means 'to draw tight'. The concept of stress was first introduced in life sciences by Hans Selye in 1936. 'Stress is the non-specific result of any demand upon the body, be the effect mental or somatic.' According to the World Health Organization, stress is a

significant problem of our times and affects both physical as well as the mental health of people. Stress is defined as a situation where the organism 's homeostasis is threatened or the organism perceives a situation as threatening. Stress coping methods are the cognitive, behavioral and psychological efforts to deal with stress. Work place stress for the teaching faculty during the accreditation process in the leading colleges place the major problems particularly women employees who take of family children and the survival of job to develop their career growth. The extension of working time, work presser in concentrating of criteria in accreditation and covering the syllabus has per work plan for the students. These are the major factors taken for research to analysis the teaching faculty attitude on health, mental attitude, job security and job turnover.

The study of Owoeye and Olatunde (2011) established that school facilities were the most potent determinant of academic achievement. They alluded that achievement is a function of availability of facilities to students in unity schools compared with public schools. Ayodele (2000) and Vandiver (2011) revealed that a positive relationship exists between availability of facilities and student academic performances. This state of affair is not different in the Ghanaian context, owing to the fact that polytechnic lecturers are expected to perform at high level in the area of curriculum without the adequate basic facilities for teaching, learning and research (Solomon et al., 2014).

Objectives:

1. To explore the relationship between variables for sources of academic stress among the teaching faculty during the accreditation process in top colleges.
2. To determine the various factors that affect the academic activities of teaching faculty during the particular situation.

Review of Related Literature

K.G. Kassymova and Agamina Zh. Kundy (2018) in their article 'Stress in Education' talks about stress management in education, the main causes and symptoms of stress and tips for reducing stress. K. Ramakrishna Rao and C. Kumar (2017) in their article entitled 'Examination Reforms to Reduce Stress among Students' the authors have defined what is examination stress, its causes and symptoms, and recommendations to reduce examination stress among students.

Dr. Jampa Venkata Rama Chandra Rao (2013) in his research paper 'Stress among Adolescent Students and Management' has identified the causes of stress among adolescent students as well as the remedial measures for stress management.

The center of di reviews the main findings of the literature on mental health, workplace hazards and working conditions. We define mental health as commonly done in reference to mental illness. However, recent research has shown that even though mental health and mental illness are related, they represent different psychological states (CDC online 2017)

Stress management programs have been characterized as red cape interventions (Polly 2014) because they have typically taken a tertiary or (at least) a secondary intervention approach. (This perspective may be changing, as more primary interventions have emerged, especially at the organization level.) Health promotion and workplace wellness programs, by contrast, may be viewed as green cape interventions because they focus on enhancing and promoting health. From a more historical perspective, however, one might take exception to this categorization. Most histories of workplace wellness programs refer back to employee assistance programs, which clearly focused on “fixing” such difficulties as alcohol and drug abuse (Frone 2013).

the erroneous conclusion that an intervention is ineffective when in fact the implementation was flawed. Nielsen and Abildgaard (2013) built on these insights to propose a longitudinal evaluation framework in which each of the intervention ‘stages’ (e.g., preparation, screening etc.,) are assessed separately to identify how it influence subsequent stages and ultimately the outcome of the intervention. They also suggested that a range of intervention outcomes (e.g., changes in attitudes, working practices and well-being) should be addressed at each stage on the basis that these changes may become evident at different times in job nature.

In some cases, allowing all employees to participate may be the only feasible way to implement the intervention. One workplace wellness program we reviewed above mandated that all employees be screened quarterly, and despite there being no penalty for not participating, the participation rate was 99% (Merrill et al. 2011). One of the major challenges for most intervention programs appears to be getting employees to participate. Short of requiring people to participate, the literature suggests that key factors include incentives, matching program components to employees’ interests, top leadership support, and a culture for health (Aldana et al. 2012).

Analysis and interpretation:

From the table 1 shows the summary of multiple regression model that state the stress of teaching faculty during the accreditation process from the table it is interpreted has Unstandardized coefficients indicate how much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant. Consider the effect of extra workload B value 1.215. The

unstandardized coefficient, B_1 equal to 0 the significance value of is 0.145 which remain constant in other aspects. This means that for each variable there is a decrease independent variables of work stress of faculty members during the process of accreditation period. Form the hypothesis reveals the model of significant F ratio (8.651) with moderate coefficient of variation of stress is explained by 6 independent variables. The above aspects not only threaten the health and the work achievement of the faculty it effects the academic and work life balance.

From the table 2 shows the Statistical analysis of mental health of faculty members and occupational stress during the time accreditation in leading colleges in Chennai city. It represents standard deviation of hypotheses difference that exist between the mental health and occupational stress of faculty members during the accreditation work in the various college. The least score is depression of anxiety 0.318 standard deviation the highest score includes the poor work balance and the faculty doesn't have time to accomplish the task in the speculative period with the standard deviation of 1.012.

From the table 3 shows the multiple regression coefficient between work related factors and the mental health factors of the faculty members shows no association with mental health outcomes, while all other risk indicators (Somatic Risk Factors, Job Content and Job Context) In contrast to the existing survey the specification the standard error and P value is low on task related work of 0.007. from this analysis it indicators the work related and mental health outcomes become the major stress among the faculty members during the accreditation process carried among the colleges.

After analyzing the data investigators have come to the following findings-

- Faculty members suggest that during the accreditation process top management should provide special tips to maintain proper work schedule, which helps them to reduce stress especially, academic stress.
- Most of the colleges can give privileges to invite special persons and arrange special motivational or inspirational talks for faculty. But majority of faculty members themselves guide the faculty and the students as and when they needed.
- Majority of colleges motivated the faculty members by providing transport, food, allowances etc. for the person who work for late hours and organize picnic or excursion, incentives, compensation leave for the faculty for the work dedication.
- However, in this paper there are many documentation aspects carried by the faculty, to balance work life balance and to carry out their academic activity to the use all the techniques many

stresses related health hazards and other medical issues, such as gastrointestinal problems, pregnancy, headache etc.

- In addition, stress management is effective for preventing behaviors such as smoking, unhealthy eating habits, sedentary lifestyle choices to name a few behaviors that serve as risk factors for the majority of the aforementioned disease and disorders.
- The stress reduction techniques taught for the faculty reflect to progressive muscle relaxation, autogenic training, relaxation response, biofeedback, guided imagery, diaphragmatic breathing, transcendental meditation, cognitive behavioral stress reduction and mindfulness-based stress reduction are all effective treatment methods for reducing stress and anxiety that accompanies daily life and to avoid chronic illness.

Implications for Practice:

Stress reduction techniques constitute a safe and effective approach for reducing stress among the faculty members. The management should provide healthcare benefits for the faculty members who dedicatedly work for the accreditation process. Faculty should provide proper training to carry the accreditation purpose it helps to avoid rewrite of work. The colleges can provider experience faculty and sufficient faculty to carry the process of accreditation to reduce stress-related symptoms can benefit for the faculty presented in this paper.

Conclusion:

There are some evidences that organization-wide approaches show the best results on individual, individual-organizational interface and organizational parameters; these comprehensive programs like accreditation have a strong impact on the entire organization, require the full support of the management. From a methodological perspective, however, it is not clear what exactly the stress causes and the job turn over effects of faculty members who work for the accreditation for the benefit of colleges. The commitment and willingness of management to invest in human resources, the quality of faculty members plays the major role to complete the task in the speculative period. Knowledge about the effectiveness of single components of stress management programmes is important, not only for the accumulation of scientific knowledge on stress prevention, but also to assist major colleges which are not in a position to implement stress reduction programmes for the faculty members who work for the development of colleges without proper work life balance. The aim of future research should be to establish credibility as to what stress management programmes can or cannot accomplish, under

circumstances. The lack of accumulation of empirical evidence and effectiveness of interventions directed towards stress prevention, is not primarily caused by a shortage of time duration of studies. While considerable heterogeneity of studies, which makes it difficult to compare various empirical studies involved in stress. There is an urgent need for better conceptualization and theoretical reflection on stress management programmes that helps to reduce stress of faculty members, it helps to avoid job turnover and work life balance particularly women employees.

Table No 1: Table show the summary of multiple regression model that state the stress of teaching faculty during the accreditation process

State of stress	Unstandardized coefficient				
	B Value	Std. error	Beta	t	Sig
Extra workload	1.215	0.827	-	1.469	0.145
Enough time to handle classes	0.953	0.133	0.265	7.174	0.00
Well-equipped resources	0.952	0.178	0.254	5.417	0.00
Enough staff loaded	0.886	0.185	0.180	4.799	0.00
Pressure in completing task	0.985	0.153	0.238	6.423	0.00
Mental stress in handling files	0.995	0.169	0.255	5.883	0.00

(Source Primary Data)

Table No 2: Statistical analysis of mental health of faculty members and occupational stress during the time accreditation in leading colleges in Chennai city

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation	MIN	MAX	N
Depression of anxiety	0.114	(0.318)	0	1	33,314
Overall fatigue	0.417	(0.493)	0	1	33,314
Sleep disorders	0.210	(0.407)	0	1	33,332
Working on weekends	3.995	(0.476)	0	7	33,355
Working on computers	3.453	(1.159)	1	7	33,375
Tiring and painful position	0.260	(0.389)	0	5	33,317
Poor work-life balance	0.400	(1.012)	1	5	33,302
Not enough time to accomplish tasks	2.059	(1.012)	1	5	33,228

(Source Primary Data)

Table No 3: Multivariate regression coefficients between work-related risk factors (Somatic Risk Factors, Job Content and Job Context) and mental health of faculty members:

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	P- Value
Depression or anxiety	0.0176	(0.0139)	0.205
Overall fatigue	-0.0188	(0.0184)	0.307
Sleep disorders	-0.0744	(0.0153)	0.629
Working on weekends	0.0115	(0.0142)	0.418
Working on computers	-0.0197	(0.0126)	0.118
Tiring and painful position	0.0231	(0.0121)	0.056
Poor work-life balance	0.0167	(0.0127)	0.188
Not enough time to accomplish tasks	0.0287	(0.0131)	0.028
Task related factors	0.0394	(0.0147)	0.007

Dealing with faculty	0.0123	(0.00782)	0.115
Hectic situation	0.0393	(0.0403)	0.329

(Source Primary Data)

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